

Anion-Exchange Selectivity Studies of Halate Ions on Amberlite IRA-400 (NO_3^-) in Aqueous Acetone Media

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Manuscript received 10 November 1980, revised 24 March 1981, accepted 20 June 1981

Anion-exchange selectivities of halate ions for a nitrate form of strongly basic exchanger Amberlite IRA-400 (20-40 mesh) have been studied in aqueous acetone solutions. The selectivity increased with increase in acetone for ClO_3^- and BrO_3^- but decreased for IO_3^- . Though the sequence of selectivity in aqueous and acetone containing solvents remained the same i.e., $\text{IO}_3^- < \text{BrO}_3^- < \text{ClO}_3^-$, the difference in selectivity ratios for the three ions increased with increasing acetone percentage. No selectivity reversal was observed upto 60% acetone media.

THE anion exchange selectivity studies in non-aqueous and mixed solvents are scant in comparison with available similar studies for cation exchange¹. The use of mixed solvents provides possibilities of selectivity reversals and better separation conditions can be evolved from such studies. Though simple halide ions have been considered for their exchange studied in mixed solvents^{2,3,4,5}, no such studies in non-aqueous and mixed solvents have been conducted for oxyanions. Diamond and Whitney⁶ have reviewed the position of such studies for oxyanions of various types in aqueous media only. They have also critically examined the various theories put forth to explain anion-exchange selectivities on the basis of available data in aqueous media only. The present work is an attempt to study three halate ions, namely chlorate, bromate and iodate in aqueous acetone media for their selectivity changes in such mixed solvent media.

Experimental

Reagents and Solutions: All halate ion solutions were prepared from their potassium salts (A.R., BDH) to give 0.1N solutions in aqueous and partly aqueous solvents. Solutions were standardised before use. Analytically pure acetone was used to prepare mixed solvent media.

Ion-Exchange resin: Air-dried strongly basic anion-exchanger, Amberlite IRA-400 (20-40 mesh) was used in nitrate form. Its capacity was found to be 4.5 meq/gm.

Determination of halate ions: Bromate and iodate ions were determined iodometrically, while chlorate ion was first reduced to chloride by ferrous sulphate solution and then determined gravimetrically as silver chloride.

Determination of selectivity coefficient: The equilibrium studies were carried out in glass stoppered Erlenmeyer flasks (150 ml) with exactly 0.5 gm of the resin and 50 ml of solution containing the halate ion (0.1M, 0.05M, 0.033M, 0.025M, 0.002M) in aqueous or aqueous acetone (10, 20, 40

and 60% v/v) solutions. Batches were equilibrated for 24 hrs with intermittent shaking. Each solution was then analysed for halate ion.

The selectivity coefficients (K_a) were calculated from the relation⁸.

$$K_a = \frac{x_{B_R}}{x_{A_R}} \cdot \frac{c_{A_W}}{c_{B_W}}$$

These values were found to vary with x_{B_R} , the equivalent fraction of the halate ion in the resin phase. Hence, the method of graphical integration was applied to evaluate the corrected selectivity coefficient K_a^B using the expression:

$$\ln K_a^B = \int_0^1 \ln K_a \cdot dx_{B_R}$$

The data is summarised in Table 1.

TABLE 1—VARIATION OF SELECTIVITY CONSTANT ($K_{\text{NO}_3^-}^{\text{XO}_3^-}$) WITH ACETONE CONCENTRATION

Acetone %	Dielectric constant	$K_{\text{NO}_3^-}^{\text{XO}_3^-}$		
		$\text{ClO}_3^-/\text{NO}_3^-$	$\text{BrO}_3^-/\text{NO}_3^-$	$\text{IO}_3^-/\text{NO}_3^-$
0	78.4	0.21	0.17	0.15
10	71.5	0.23	0.19	0.09
20	66.0	0.26	0.19	0.05
40	54.3	0.39	0.23	0.035
60	42.5	0.56	0.31	P.Pt.*

* P.Pt. indicates precipitation or insolubility of the electrolyte in mixed solvents.

The free energies of exchange (ΔF^0) have also been calculated and tabulated in Table 2.

TABLE 2—FREE ENERGIES OF EXCHANGE FOR HALATE/NITRATE EXCHANGES AT 30° IN VARIOUS ACETONE-WATER MEDIA

Acetone % v/v	ΔF^0 , cal. mole ⁻¹			Selectivity sequence
	$\text{ClO}_3^-/\text{NO}_3^-$	$\text{BrO}_3^-/\text{NO}_3^-$	$\text{IO}_3^-/\text{NO}_3^-$	
0	+933	+1086	+1156	$\text{IO}_3^- < \text{BrO}_3^- < \text{ClO}_3^-$
10	+894	+1015	+1450	$\text{IO}_3^- < \text{BrO}_3^- < \text{ClO}_3^-$
20	+807	+996	+1833	$\text{IO}_3^- < \text{BrO}_3^- < \text{ClO}_3^-$
40	+565	+898	+2022	$\text{IO}_3^- < \text{BrO}_3^- < \text{ClO}_3^-$
60	+352	+711	—	— $\text{BrO}_3^- < \text{ClO}_3^-$

Discussion

The variability of the observed selectivity coefficients (K_a) with the equivalent fractions of the halate ions in the resin phase (x_{B_R}) in the present studies (like that of Bhatnagar *et al*² for halide/hydroxyl exchange in aqueous ethanol) led us to evaluate corrected selectivity coefficients K_a^B by the method of graphical integration.

Gupta *et al*⁸ have justified and used the method of graphical integration in mixed solvent media. They have also shown that the method can be applied provided the electrolyte concentration is $\leq 0.1N$ and the organic solvent concentration is upto $\sim 50\%$. As the present experimental conditions were within these limits evaluation of $K_{NO_3^-}^{XO_3^-}$ in aqueous acetone media by this method was well justified.

The data in Table 1 indicates clearly that the corrected selectivity coefficient increases regularly with acetone percentage for ClO_3^-/NO_3^- and BrO_3^-/NO_3^- exchanges while it decreases for IO_3^-/NO_3^- exchange. If graphs are plotted for $K_{NO_3^-}^{XO_3^-}$ against the acetone percentage on volume to volume basis, they show a curvilinear nature and show more exchange for ClO_3^- as compared to BrO_3^- or IO_3^- against the nitrate ion in the resin phase. In all cases the sequence of selectivity as measured by $K_{NO_3^-}^{XO_3^-}$ remained the same i.e., $IO_3^- < BrO_3^- < ClO_3^-$. No selectivity reversal was observed upto 60% acetone concentration. Aveston *et al*⁹ and Kikindai¹⁰ have given the same selectivity sequence for halate ions in aqueous media studies. All these ions studied in aqueous acetone media (upto 60% v/v) have shown less preference for the exchanger in nitrate ionic form as the selectivity constants evaluated were all less than unity.

The evaluation of free energies of exchange (Table 2) justified the same selectivity trends. The ΔF° values for ClO_3^-/NO_3^- and BrO_3^-/NO_3^- exchanges were showing a decrease with increasing organic solvent concentration or lowered dielectric constants of the media. However, these trends were just opposite for IO_3^-/NO_3^- exchange. Graphs for $K_{NO_3^-}^{XO_3^-}$ versus the reciprocal dielectric constant of the solvent systems were all linear (figures omitted) showing a regular increase in selectivities for ClO_3^-/NO_3^- and BrO_3^-/NO_3^- exchanges and a decrease for IO_3^-/NO_3^- exchange selectivities. As per Pauley's model¹¹ for an ion-exchange system, it is expected that the selectivity coefficient should show always an increase with decrease in the dielectric constant of the system. Davydov¹² has applied this concept for NO_3^-/Cl^- exchange in aqueous ethanol also. However this does not appear to be true for halate type of ions or oxyanions in general.

The point of interest in these selectivity trends is the change in separation ratio of selectivity constants (corrected) with change in solvent composition.

These selectivity constants gave less separation for IO_3^- , BrO_3^- and ClO_3^- in aqueous solutions (the ratio being 1.0 : 1.1 : 1.4) as compared to those obtained in mixed systems. This increased with increasing acetone percentage (v/v) in the solvent media so much that the ratio became 1.0 : 6.5 : 11.1 for halate ions in 40% acetone solutions. Thus mixed solvents can be of much greater utility for planning separation of these ions.

Many theories have been proposed to explain anion-exchange selectivity orders in aqueous medium⁶. Though the dependance of selectivity order on the polarizability of ions was satisfactory to show $F^- < Cl^- < Br^- < I^-$ selectivity sequence for simple halide ions, the concept failed to explain the observed order of selectivities for halates^{9,10}. The observed effect was opposite to what was expected from the anion-refractions used as a measure of ion polarizabilities. This concept also failed to explain the sequence for other oxyanions such as $ReO_4^- < TeO_4^- < MnO_4^-$ ^{9,13,14} and $TeO_3^{2-} < SeO_3^{2-} < S_2O_3^{2-}$ ¹⁵.

The suggestion that the resin selectivity is due to some sort of clustered ion-pairing near the sites already paired, has also been discarded on the basis of the fact that the selectivity coefficients for ClO_4^-/Cl^- , ReO_4^-/Cl^- and CNS^-/Cl^- did not increase strongly with increasing resin mole fraction of the ion of interest.

Anion-exchange selectivities have been explained in a much better way by considering the suggestions of Diamond and Whitney⁶ regarding the effects of water structure on ion-water, ion-counter ion and counter ion-resin matrix interactions. Thus ion-water interaction explains the halide ion sequence quite well as the hydration in these ions goes on decreasing in the order of their increasing preference for the resin phase. But Chu *et al*¹⁶ have given a different type of reasoning for halate type of polyatomic anions. They have suggested that base strength of the anions should be taken as a criterion for the resin's preference for the ion. If an anion picks up a proton, it has stronger interaction with water and consequently it prefers the water phase over the resin phase. Thus an anion which is a stronger base prefers the water phase, while the one which is a weaker base prefers the resin phase.

The base strength for oxyanions derived from halogens increases from chlorate to iodate. The iodate has a property of taking up protons more strongly than bromate and bromate has this tendency more than chlorate.

On the basis of this concept, therefore, iodate should prefer the water phase more as compared to bromate or chlorate, showing least resin selectivity out of the three halates studied. The observed sequence in aqueous solutions is thus justified.

In water-acetone media the above mentioned sequence is retained though the actual selectivity coefficient values showed a change. Hence, it may be concluded that their respective base strength

sequences are maintained in these mixed solvent systems also, though their actual pK values must be undergoing progressive changes due to changes in the dielectric constants of the solvent systems. Increase in selectivity coefficients with increase in acetone concentration in the solvent system further confirms that these ions become less preferred by the solution phase due to its disturbed water structure. The decrease in the exchange of IO_3^- seemingly is due to lesser dissociation of its potassium salt in the mixed media of increasing acetone concentration. This electrolyte actually gave precipitation at 60% acetone concentration (Table 1) in solution phase. Thus it appears that the concept of Chu *et al*⁶ is a much better concept to explain exchange selectivities for oxyanions in aqueous as well as in mixed solvent systems.

References

1. Y. MARCUS, in "Ion-Exchange and Solvent Extraction", Vol. 4, Marcel Dekker Inc., New York, 1973, 71.
2. R. P. BHATNAGAR, R. C. ARORA and S. C. MALIK, *Z. Physk. Chem.*, 1963, **222**, 311.
3. C. V. KRISHNAN and P. S. RAMANATHAN, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1967, **5**, 551.
4. A. M. PHIPPS, *Anal. Chem.*, 1968, **40**, 1769.
5. G. I. STAROBINETS and G. N. BULATSKAYA, *Vestn. Akad. Navuk Belarus, SSR. Ser. Khim. Navuk.*, 1969(3), 106.
6. R. M. DIAMOND and D. C. WHITNEY, in "Ion Exchange", Vol. 1, Marcel Dekker Inc, New York, 1966.
7. T. R. E. KRESSMAN and J. A. KITCHENER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 1190.
8. A. R. GUPTA, M. R. GHATE and S. SHANKER, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1968, **6**, 98.
9. J. AVRSTON, D. A. EVEREST and R. A. WELLS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 231.
10. M. KIKINDAI, *Compt. Rend.*, 1955, **140**, 1100.
11. J. L. PAULEY, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 1622.
12. A. T. DAVYDOV, *Ukn. Khim. Zhur.*, 1963, **29**, 358.
13. R. W. ATTERBURY and G. E. BOYD, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 4805.
14. R. N. SEN SARMA, E. ANDERS and J. W. MILLER, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1959, **63**, 559.
15. A. IGUCHI, *Bull. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1958, **31**, 748.
16. B. CHU, D. C. WHITNEY and R. M. DIAMOND, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1962 **24**, 1405.